

TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPING PATRIOTISM IN FUTURE MILITARY EDUCATION TEACHERS.

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Annotation. In this article, historical and contemporary methods of developing patriotism of future military education teachers thoughts about relevance are held.

Key words: military education, patriotism, armed forces.

In the conditions of reforming the field of military education in our country, patriotism has not lost its importance as a moral. The content of patriotism is multifaceted, it is the formation of a feeling of love for one's motherland and pride for one's people. Also, preserving the country's wealth means contributing to the improvement of the people's life in difficult life situations or in everyday life. One of the directions of patriotic education is determined by the impact on the mind, emotions, will and spirit of future teachers in the pedagogical process. The system of formation and development of patriotism includes:

- citizenship and patriotism education;
- moral education;
- sports competitions;

The purpose of the civic-patriotic directions is manifested in the formation of civil position, norms of moral behavior, responsibility, service to the country in future military education teachers. One of the serious relations in the educational process is the organization of patriotic events, and the direction of military patriotism includes the following:

- conducting city, district and regional competitions, military sports competitions throughout the year;

love for one's homeland, readiness to defend it, strong courage;

- formation of patriotic feelings along with manifestation of courage and determination;
- to develop a desire to serve the country in difficult situations;
- increasing military training;

education of moral qualities such as honesty, nobility, humility;

- community, desire to do good, active resistance to evil;
- respect for public interests and mutual respect. All this is part of the individual's military culture and should be planned in a specific way.

The literature analysis shows that under the concept of "Military Patriotism".

in one case, the love of the majority is given to their homeland, people and mother nature in the first place, and in another case, loyalty to other peoples is emphasized along with respect. The manifestation of patriotism is determined, first of all, by the formation of a sense of national pride. It is necessary to pay attention to personal psychology in the development of patriotism in future military education teachers. The qualities that determine its direction are divided into three:

- the first group-descriptive qualities. A person's attitude to himself, to other people, to society as a whole;
- the second group-descriptive qualities. A person's attitude to various types of activities (work, study, play, etc.). That is, diligence, perseverance, determination, discipline, diligence, etc.;

The third group is characterizing qualities. Man's attitude to various material values (nature), objects, tools, and labor products): thrift, neatness, economy, etc. Based on these classifications, we came to the conclusion that patriotism manifests itself in a person's attitude to the community, society, and the ability to preserve material values. Accordingly, at the initial stage, a program of patriotic education of military personnel was developed.

Analysis of the content of the events and the development of military patriotism among young people is the main focus. Discussions on the history of the country, the moral image of the military, compliance with the rules set in the military field, the promotion of the military in Uzbekistan, and the participation of teams in international competitions are being ensured. a number of practical works are being carried out, now many reserve officers are giving their knowledge and skills to the students. The process of mastering (students' activities) consists of a two-sided process. In the process of teaching military training, he organizes familiarization with students and practical activities. Students' activities in the process of mastering will consist of acquiring knowledge, skills and competencies.

The teaching process is closely connected with the educational process. This means that not only knowledge, skills and competences are formed in students, but also students are brought up on the basis of the idea of national independence, love and patriotism for the Armed Forces and military service are formed in them.

The primary and leading element of the content of the teaching process is knowledge. Acquiring knowledge means studying subjects, situations, concepts and laws. It is important for students not to learn specific facts, but to acquire a clear system of knowledge. For example, if students know the parts of a Kalashnikov assault rifle, but do not know their interaction in a combat situation, this cannot be considered satisfactory.

Formation of skills and competence is a component of the educational process. Skill means performing a set of actions in accordance with the tasks and conditions set on the basis of the knowledge acquired by students. Students should be able to perform these actions not only in this situation, but also when the initial conditions are changed.

An example of skill formation is determining the azimuth using a map. Skill is formed by repeating one action many times. The teaching process is carried out in a clear sequence.

The stages of such a sequence are as follows: setting a task before students, creating interest in knowledge, acceptance of new material by students, reflection of the received material, generalization, formation of scientific concepts, assimilation of laws, strengthening and improvement of acquired knowledge, formation of skills and competences, application of knowledge, skills and competences, examination of acquired knowledge, skills and competences of students, analysis of teaching results.

This scheme of training is considered conditional and does not exclude other possible links of training. The future teacher of military training needs to know well the requirements of didactics, to which the entire educational process is subject, and it is necessary to use these laws to successfully achieve educational and educational goals.

In didactics, the following basic principles, which are common to teaching all subjects, are collected: scientific, developmental and educational nature of teaching, consciousness and activity in teaching, connection of theory with practice, systematic and sequence in teaching. flexibility, demonstration in teaching, solidity of knowledge, skills and abilities, individual approach, etc. All these principles are closely related and complement each other in the teaching process.

Scientific principle. This principle envisages that in the process of teaching students, they should acquire science-proven knowledge that can meet the current level of development of science. The principle of scientism envisages a critical assessment of foreign, erroneous ideas, views and concepts that are contrary to the ideals of independence.

Educative and developmental nature of teaching. Based on this principle, the military education teacher not only comes up with questions on science while conducting educational work, but also, during the educational process, it is necessary to educate the student in the spirit of ideological - political and military - patriotism. must choose materials. Training well-rounded and reliable defenders of our independent homeland is not only about equipping students with knowledge, skills and abilities, but also means training in them such qualities as observation, vigilance, physical strength, ability to overcome any hardships encountered during work and service.

Also, in the pedagogical process, it is possible to teach students about patriotism, heroism in front of the country, and to develop the qualities of bravery and courage by having a psychological effect, so that the feeling of patriotism and love turns into a true belief, a true creed. For example, the old Shaykh Najmuddin Kubro became the leader himself, formed an army from the vengeful people, and mobilized the citizens of Urganch to fight against the enemy. There will be a fierce and merciless battle between the two sides. Then the Shaykh held the flag until his last breath. They had to cut off the Shaikh's fingers one by one to get the flag. The strength, health, invincibility, faith, and physical health of the country depend on the patriotism of our youth. Our grandfather Amir Temur paid a lot of attention to this aspect of the issue when creating an army: "I followed three rules when creating and managing a army (troop, military structure): first - the strength of a young man; secondly - to be able to play with a sword; thirdly - to his intelligence and maturity. If I have these three qualities, I will be hired as a servant. After all, a strong young man is resistant to all difficulties and sufferings, a person who can play with a sword can defeat his opponent, and a smart craftsman can use his intelligence everywhere and overcome difficulties." [1]

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